

Determinants of Retail Investor Awareness towards Indian Stock Market: An Empirical Approach

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Abstract

The present study aims at to study the awareness of investors on stock market investment. The data were collected from 180 retail investors in Madurai district using a well structured questionnaire. The analysis is done with factor analysis and mean ranking. Test results indicated that four factors have emerged to indicate retail investor's awareness namely financial aspects, Recommendations, Fundamental data and Risk Return. The study proves that Financial aspects is the important dimension perceived by the respondents.

Keywords: Awareness, behavioural finance, investment decision, stock market.

Introduction

Indian investors are good savers, but often lose hard-earned money due to lack of knowledge and understanding about the financial products and financial markets. The best form of investor protection is investor awareness and the best way to achieve that is through financial literacy. Hence, the investor should be knowledgeable, cautious and they should know the changing conditions of market scenario well before making an investment in the stock market. A study of the savings and investment pattern, their perceptions and preferences, thus, assumes a larger significance in the formulation of policies for the development and regulation of the securities market in general and the protection and promotion of investors' interest in particular. It is expected that the current study will deliver valuable insights and assistance to market regulators and preparers in improving corporate sources of information and, in turn, preparers could form their information sources to the needs of its users. This is essential in order for the corporations to keep current and attract more investments.

Objectives

1. To identify the important factors determining the awareness of retail investors towards stock market
2. To identify the most important factor using mean ranking

Literature Review

Kadariya Collins et al. (2012) studied the level of awareness and found that the investors' awareness level was found to be affected by the related work experience, understanding of investment environment, learning expectation and access to market information; there was a positive relationship between investors' awareness and equity investment;

Banumathy, K. And Azhagaiah (2016) through their study proved that there is a significant difference between male and female investors on awareness of stock market investment; there is a significant difference among the age, educational and occupational groups with respect to awareness; there is also a significant difference among the investors of different age and occupational groups, in respect of awareness.

Alanezi, F., Alfraih, M., & Almujaed, H. (2014) ,found that the most important sources of information to the Kuwaiti multi-investors was "general corporate information was information about major types of product (services), and for "financial information," it was operating profit. In addition, the most important item in "non-financial information" was new contracts won by the company. Furthermore, the most important item in "corporate governance information" was corporate strategies. Moreover, the most important item in "corporate social information" was improvement in customer services.

Alanezi, F., Alfraih, M., & Almujaed, H. (2014) , The findings of this study reveal that individuals' income has shown significant influences of determining their investment behaviour. Further findings reveal that individuals' income is directly proportional to their financial literacy.

Nagy, A., & Obenberger, W. (2014). , Examination of the various utility-maximization and behavioural variables under-lying individual investor behavior provides more comprehensive understanding of the investment decisions process.

Deene, S. (2014). , Most of the small individual investors had given unfavorable opinion with regards to the capital market. Majority of small individual investors said the level of satisfaction/ experiences with the capital market is poor.

Saranya et al. [49] explored this study is to estimated that the most positive option in which people like to invested their savings and which factors do usually measured by people while making investments in offered avenues. The returns and risk concerned in investment in currency market should obviously intimate to the investors during various channels of statement to avoid the story and loss to the investors [50]. Conclude that the high-income group is ready to get more risk in investment but the middle and lower-income group considered the risk involved in investment and safety of investment as the main aspect

Maruthu Pandian. P, Benjamin Christopher , (2010), conducted a study entitled, "A Study on Equity Investor Awareness" in order to study the stock . The research work found that the awareness index is high among young male investor, post-graduates and meticulous business men.

Research Methodology

To study the investors' awareness about investment in stock market, a well structured questionnaire was prepared and was administered to the retail investors in Madurai district. The questionnaire was distributed through personal contacts and through E-mails. The questionnaires were distributed to the clients of various stock broking agencies in Madurai and 180 valid responses were received. The collected primary data were analyzed by applying various statistical tools such as factor analysis and mean ranking.

Results and Discussion

To identify the pertinent dimensions representing the determinants of retail investor awareness, 15 statements pertaining to awareness on stock markets have been carefully selected on prior literature survey. A principal component analysis was carried out. The validity of the factor analysis is examined with the values of Kaiser-meyer-ohlin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of Sphericity. The KMO value is .842 and Bartlett's test is significant. The factor analysis resulted in four key dimensions. The total number of variables loaded in each factor, its reliability, Eigen value and the per cent of variance explained by the factor are explained in Table 1.

Table 1 – Rotated Component Matrix

Factors	Variables	Factor Loading	Reliability Coefficient	Eigen Value	Variance in Percentage
Advice / Recommendations	Brokerage firms / Distributors	.956	.881	3.804	23.777
	Friends / Relatives	.958			
	Media (TV & Business Websites)	.953			
	Individual Agents	.939			
Financial Aspects	Balance Sheet	.888	.876	3.108	19.427
	Annual Reports	.732			
	Quarterly Earnings	.769			
	Various Ratios	.887			
Risk & Return	Calculated Risk	.935	.901	2.680	16.749
	Expected Return	.907			
	Financial Goals	.931			
Fundamental Reasons	Dividend Policy	.786	.794	2.593	16.208
	Price of Shares	.856			
	Valuations	.772			
	Tax Planning	.720			
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy = .842					
Bartlett's test of Sphericity : Chi Square = 7305.881*					

Mean Ranking test results revealed that among the four factors, "Financial Aspects" secured the first rank with the highest mean score (M= 3.89), followed by "Fundamental reasons" (M=3.78), Risk & Return (M = 3.75) and "Recommendations" (M=3.55) occupying the second, third and fourth ranks respectively.

Conclusion

Investment is considered as an individual's commitment for funds to derive future income in the form of interest, dividends, rent, premium, pension benefits or appreciation of the value of their principle capital. Most of the investments are considered to transfers of financial assets from one person to another. The findings suggest that Financial data are important to investors, even though investors employ diverse criteria when choosing stocks.. The recommendations of brokerage houses, individual stock brokers, family members and co-workers go largely unheeded. Many individual investors discount the benefits of valuation models when evaluating stocks.

References

1. Banumathy, K. And Azhagaiah (2016). Investors Awareness About Investment in Stock Market, 8(11), 14–22.
2. Kadariya, S. Prasad, P. S. Joshi, B. & Prasad, R. N. (2012). Investor awareness and investment on equity in Nepalese capital market. Banking Journal, 2(1), 1- invested their money only in SM therefore, further studies 15.
3. Alanezi, F., Alfraih, M., & Almujaed, H. (2014). Kuwait Stock Market Participants' Perceptions of Information Useful to the Investment Decisions, 9(6), 58–71. <http://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v9n6p58>
4. Alanezi, F., Alfraih, M., & Almujaed, H. (2014). Kuwait Stock Market Participants' Perceptions of Information Useful to the Investment Decisions, 9(6), 58–71. <http://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v9n6p58>
5. Nagy, A., & Obenberger, W. (2014). Influencing Individual Behavior Investor, 50(4), 63–68.
6. Deene, S. (2014). i a e m e investors perceptions and preferences for capital market: evidences from india, 6502, 69–78.
7. Maruthu Pandian P, Benjamin Christopher S, “A study on Equity Investor Awareness”, Doctoral Dissertation at Bharathiar University, 2011.